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Tiered multi-objective optimization of CO₂ transport for CCS

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Abstract

To accelerate the deployment of Carbon Capture and Sequestration (CCS), as a key technology for mitigating global warming, affordable and efficient CO₂ transport solutions are urgently needed for implementation in industrial clusters. Finding these solutions requires balancing the transport technology costs against several other factors, including public acceptance, environmental impacts, safety, financial and operational risks, and construction time. In this study, a Tiered Multi-Objective Optimization (TMOO) method was developed to provide decision makers with a tool for systematically evaluating and ranking the CO₂ transport solutions. In the model, the cost of CO₂ transport was calculated from techno-economic analysis, while the environmental impacts on global warming, biodiversity, and human health are evaluated using life cycle assessment. A weighted sum method is applied to combine the financial costs and environmental impacts for the Pareto multi-objective optimization. The TMOO method was applied to determine optimal strategies for aggregation of CO₂ from five large industrial emitters in the North Sea Port (NSP) region, as a case study. Realistic CO₂ infrastructure design cases were considered, involving shipping and pipeline transport and conditioning for subsequent transportation to outside the cluster region at -30 °C and 20 bar. In all the cases at the emission sources, the CO₂ was assumed to be at 5 bar and 40 °C. The results show that a low pressure (35 bar) CO₂ collection pipeline is the optimal solution, with the lowest cost (€12.5/tCO₂) and global warming impact (22.9 kgCO₂-eq/tCO₂), followed by ship 'hub and spoke' as a second preferable solution that comes at higher costs and environmental impacts. To help identify potential alternatives for CO₂ transport in the region, ranking of sub-optimal solutions, involving higher pressure (110 bar) pipelines and 'milk-round' shipping of CO₂, was performed. Across all the CO₂ transport cases studied, electricity consumed for CO₂ compression and liquefaction was found to make the largest contribution to costs (ca 44%) and environmental impacts (ca 96%).

Keywords: CO₂ transport; pipeline; shipping; costs; life cycle analysis; tiered multi-objective optimization

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1. Introduction

Carbon Capture and Sequestration (CCS) is a key set of technologies being developed to mitigate the impact of CO₂ emissions on the global warming [1], [2,3]. It is part of a portfolio of strategies needed to decarbonize the hard to abate energy-intensive industries and the power generation sector to reach net-zero emission reduction targets set by the EU for 2050 [4]. To achieve this, CCS technologies are expected to play an important role in the near-future decarbonization of industrial clusters, such as the North Sea Port (NSP) cluster which emits over 21 Mt of CO₂ annually [5,6]. Despite the clear urgency of the need for CCS, there are significant barriers to CCS deployment, namely, the lack of investment initiatives and CO₂ transport infrastructure, as well as high costs [7]. To overcome these barriers, particularly the financial risks for first-of-a-kind projects, suitable methods and tools for evaluating the potential of various CO₂ infrastructure solutions, including using modular/mobile modes of CO₂ transport for the near-future implementation in industrial clusters, are urgently needed.

Nomenclature

c	annualised cost of CO ₂ transport and conditioning (€/y)
C	the lifetime cost of CO ₂ conditioning and transport (€/tCO ₂)
C^{ship}	specific cost of shipping (€/tCO ₂)
$C^{tonnage}$	the shipping tonnage cost (€/tCO ₂)
$C^{mileage}$	the shipping mileage cost (€/tCO ₂ ·km)
$J_{i,k}$	normalized objective functions ($i=1 \dots 4$) for the design case k
l_i	shipping distance on the i^{th} route (km)
$O_{j,k}$	dimensional objective functions ($i=1 \dots 4$) for the design case k
q	the annual throughput of a pipeline system (t/y)
q_i	the CO ₂ flow rate from the i^{th} emitter (tCO ₂ /y)
S	the interim storage capacity (tCO ₂)
t_i^{cycle}	the roundtrip sailing time on the i^{th} route (h)
v^{ship}	the ship speed (km/h)
$\mathbf{w} = (w_1, w_2, w_3, w_4)$	the vector of weighting factors for the objective functions

High-pressure pipelines are commonly considered to be the lowest-cost option for transporting large quantities of CO₂ [8]. In the case of industrial clusters with multiple emitters aiming for the same storage location, using shared CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure has been shown to significantly reduce the transportation costs and hence the economic risks for the cluster [9,10]. However, the uncertainty in the quantities of CO₂ captured from industrial installations in the long term and the high initial investments required for shared pipeline infrastructure may make decentralized CO₂ transport solutions more attractive. For transportation of small amounts of CO₂ and short-duration projects, mobile modes of CO₂ transport, such as trucks, barges and ships, has been found to be more economical than pipelines [11,12], while offering greater flexibility [13–15]. Low-pressure pipelines transporting gaseous CO₂ can be more economical for short-distance transport [16]. Also, shipping CO₂ captured from emitters in a CCS cluster to a collection hub for subsequent off-shore pipeline transport is shown to be more economical than shipping CO₂ from the individual emitters to the off-shore storage location [14]. Importantly, however, the cost of a transport mode is not a unique criterion that drives the decision making when choosing a specific solution for CO₂ transport in CCS projects. Other important criteria that are considered when planning for CO₂ transport infrastructure include, among others, public acceptance, the environmental impact, safety, financial and operational risks, as well as the project duration and construction time [17]. In particular, although the contribution of CO₂ transport to the environmental impact of CCS is commonly thought to be relatively small, a recent study performed for CO₂ transport chains connecting Switzerland and Norway [18] showed that environmental footprint of the fossil fuel-operated ready-to-use mobile CO₂ transport can be significant (*ca.* 56% of the CCS chain), resulting in sequestration of *ca.* 76% CO₂ [18].

To balance the various factors in the design optimization of CCS chains, multi-objective decision analysis can be applied (see [19], [20]). Using multi-objective optimization approach can be particularly useful for balancing costs

and environmental impacts of CO₂ transport against other factors including speed of deployment of the CO₂ transport infrastructure. This is especially important given that for various CO₂ transport modes, such as pipelines and ships/barges, which are most relevant for many industrial CCS clusters in coastal regions of the North Sea [21–23], costs and environmental impacts may not correlate, hence requiring evaluation on a case-by-case basis.

In this context, the present study is aimed at (a) developing a multi-objective optimization method for systematic evaluation of costs and environmental impacts of CO₂ transport solutions for CCS clusters implementing the well-established methods of Techno-Economic Assessment (TEA) and LCA, and (b) applying this method to compare the performance of realistic CO₂ transport strategies involving shared pipeline infrastructure and barges, proposed for aggregation of CO₂ in the North Sea Port (NSP) cluster prior to its subsequent transport to geological storage locations.

2. Methodology

2.1. Aims and scope

In the present work, TEA and LCA were applied to assess the financial costs and environmental impacts of CO₂ transport infrastructure collecting CO₂ from five large emitters in the NSP industrial cluster, including ArcelorMittal Ghent (AMG) steel plant, DOW chemical plant, Zeeland Refinery (ZR), Yara ammonia and fertilizer plant and Engie Electrabel (EE) power station [24,25]. Figure 1 shows the NSP region along with locations and projected 2030 CO₂ emissions from the five cluster industries considered in the present study.

Figure 1. Map showing the NSP area borders (yellow lines, <https://northseaport.maps.arcgis.com/home/index.html>) and also the locations (dots) and the projected 2030 CO₂ capture rates from five major NSP industries considered in the present study.

Two CO₂ transport modes, namely pipelines and barges, were considered realistic and modelled for the NSP cluster. Four strategies implementing the two chosen modes of transport were considered for further optimization, including using low-pressure and high-pressure pipelines, and ‘hub and spoke’ and ‘milk round’ strategies for CO₂ collection by barges, as illustrated in Figure 2. Table 1 lists all the 10 cases constructed for the study, stating the CO₂ transport conditions for each strategy. Given significant experience with commercial transport of food grade CO₂ at ‘mid pressure’ 20 bar and –30 °C, the latter conditions were chosen for shipping scenarios and the onward transport of CO₂. Two off-take points were also considered for both modes of transport, at Yara and at AMG. In the hub and spoke shipping strategy each emitter was assumed to be serviced individually, while in the milk round strategy a single

ship was assumed to collect CO₂ from the chain of emitters in a circuit. For the latter strategy, both north and south directions were considered for each off-take point.

Table 1. Conditions and design specifications for CO₂ transport cases studied. For onward transport, the CO₂ was conditioned at –30°C and 20 bar for all cases.

Case number	Mode of CO ₂ transport	Transport strategy	Off-take point	Direction of flow	Temperature (°C)	Pressure (bar)	Interim storage at capture points
1	Pipeline	Low pressure	Yara	-	30	35	No
2	Pipeline	High pressure	Yara	-	30	110	No
3	Pipeline	Low pressure	AMG	-	30	35	No
4	Pipeline	High pressure	AMG	-	30	110	No
5	Ship	Hub and spoke	Yara	-	-30	20	Yes
6	Ship	Hub and spoke	AMG	-	-30	20	Yes
7	Ship	Milk round	Yara	North	-30	20	Yes
8	Ship	Milk round	Yara	South	-30	20	Yes
9	Ship	Milk round	AMG	North	-30	20	Yes
10	Ship	Milk round	AMG	South	-30	20	Yes

Figure 2. The four intra-cluster CO₂ transport strategies: (a) 35 bar pipeline, (b) 110 bar pipeline, (c) shipping, hub and spoke, and (d) shipping, milk round (south) with the off-take at AMG, implementing the infrastructure elements, including compression, liquefaction, pipelines, ships, and interim storage. The arrows indicate the direction of CO₂ flow on transport routes. The green dashed lines indicate the system boundaries.

Figure 2 shows schematically the topology and infrastructure required for the four strategies from Table 1 with the off-take at AMG. For LCA, the gate-to-gate system boundaries were used, focusing on the intra-cluster CO₂ transport from the point of CO₂ capture to the point of CO₂ collection for long-distance transport outside the NSP. CO₂ capture, terminal storage, and onward transport outside the NSP were not included in the study. For all the strategies, it was assumed that at each source the captured CO₂ is available at 5 bar and 40 °C and has high purity. The liquid CO₂ conditions for transport and hub storage were chosen based on the literature recommendations and specifications for planned projects [14,21,26]. At the end of intra-cluster transportation, the CO₂ is assumed to be liquefied for terminal storage for onward transport at 20 bar and –30 °C.

To establish a common reference between and across the TEA and LCA, the analysis is performed for a common functional unit of 1 tonne of CO₂ conditioned, stored and transported within the NSP cluster region from the capture plants to an off-take point for onward shipping.

2.2. TEA of CO₂ transport

In the case of pipeline transport, the lifetime cost of intra-cluster CO₂ conditioning (compression and liquefaction of high-purity CO₂) and transport (€/t_{CO2}) was calculated following [27]:

$$C = \frac{c^{compression} + c^{liquefaction} + c^{pipeline} + c^{re-compression}}{q} \quad (1)$$

where q is the annual throughput of the pipeline (t/y) and each cost term in the numerator was calculated as a sum of CAPEX, variable OPEX and fixed OPEX, all in (€/y) as detailed in Table 2. When calculating the variable OPEX costs, electricity price of €125/MWh was assumed. The pipeline sizes were optimized in order to minimize the lifetime costs, defined as the sum of pipeline CAPEX and the OPEX [28]. The lifetime of the pipeline and storage infrastructure was set at 25 years. CAPEX was annualized using a capital recovery factor of 9.4 % (25 years payback period at 8% interest rate) [27]. The compressor CAPEX model accounts for economies of scale, hence costs are calculated for each compressor specified on the network (see Figure 2). For liquefaction, the specific CAPEX term (€/t_{CO2}/y) in Table 2 was multiplied by q for unit consistency.

For shipping, the lifetime cost of CO₂ conditioning and transport was calculated as:

$$C = \frac{c^{compression} + c^{liquefaction} + c^{storage}}{q} + C^{ship} \quad (2)$$

where, in addition to the terms already covered in equation (4), the cost of ship(s) was calculated as:

$$C^{ship} = C^{tonnage} + \frac{\sum_i l_i q_i}{\sum_i q_i} C^{mileage} \quad (3)$$

Here, the tonnage cost $C^{tonnage}$ (€/t_{CO2}) and mileage cost $C^{mileage}$ (€/t_{CO2}·km) were taken from [29]. In equation (2), the cost of storage comprises CAPEX (calculated as the product of the specific CAPEX in Table 2 and the interim storage capacity S) and fixed OPEX. The interim storage capacity S (t_{CO2}) for the hub and spoke (H&S) and the milk round (MR) strategies were calculated as:

$$S^{H\&S} = f^{oper} \sum_i q_i t_i^{cycle} \quad (4)$$

$$S^{MR} = f^{oper} \sum_i t_i^{cycle} \sum_i q_i \quad (5)$$

where q_i is the CO₂ flow rate from the i^{th} emitter (t_{CO2}/y), $f^{oper} = 1.2$ is the operational flexibility factor [26] and t_i^{cycle} is the roundtrip sailing time (h) for the shipping run on the i^{th} route:

$$t_i^{cycle} = \frac{l_i f^{load-unload}}{v^{ship}} \quad (6)$$

Here l_i is the shipping distance on the i^{th} route in km, obtained using the Python package Searoute [30], v^{ship} is the ship speed (20 km/h) and $f^{\text{load-unload}} = 1.4$ is the loading and unloading factor [26].

The tonnage cost C^{tonnage} (€/t_{CO2}) is scale-dependent (based on thresholds in terms of t_{CO2}/y carried on the route), hence calculated per route for the hub and spoke strategy.

Table 2. Cost parameters used in the TEA and their sources. Figures have been converted from original currency to 2023 €. *Scale: 250-1500 kt_{CO2}/y per route, ** Scale: 1500-2500 kt_{CO2}/y per route, *** Scale: 2500-30000 kt_{CO2}/y per route, † Mean of CAPEX estimates for 70 bar inlet, 14-40 bar outlet pressures, ‡ Mean values, # Assumed in the present study.

Terms in equations (1) & (2)	Infrastructure element	Mode of CO ₂ transport	CAPEX	OPEX	Reference
C^{pipeline}	Pipeline	Pipeline	€, Empirical non-linear model based on pipe length and outer diameter	3% of CAPEX/y	[28], [32]
$C^{\text{re-compression}}$	Booster compressors/ pumps	Pipeline, Ship	€, Empirical scaling model	4% of CAPEX/y	[31]
$C^{\text{compression}}$	5-stage compression	Pipeline, Ship	€, Empirical scaling model	€125/ MWh #	[31]
C^{storage}	Interim storage	Ship	1140 €/t _{CO2}	5% of CAPEX/y	[26]
$C^{\text{liquefaction}}$	Liquefaction	Pipeline, Ship	14.1 €/(t _{CO2} /y) †	7.5% of CAPEX/y ‡	[26]
C^{ship}	Barges	Ship	C^{tonnage} : 14.7 €/t _{CO2} * 13.6 €/t _{CO2} ** 9.0 €/t _{CO2} ***	C^{mileage} : 0.0069 €/t _{CO2} .km	[29]

2.3. LCA of CO₂ transport

The LCA was conducted in four steps, as defined in ISO 14044 [34]. First, in the goal and scope step, the functional unit, relevant processes and system boundaries (see Section 2.1) and the LCA aims were defined. Then, for all the flows going in (e.g., energy and materials) and out (e.g., emissions and waste) of the system boundaries, across the life cycle of the processes modeled, the relevant data were collected in the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) step. The LCI data was then converted to environmental impacts and organized into impact categories in the Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) step. Finally, the outcomes of the LCI and the LCIA are systematically evaluated (see Section 3).

For the transport cases studied (see Table 1), the foreground LCI data were collected for CO₂ conditioning (compression and liquefaction), shipping, pipeline transport, and storage as summarized in Table 3. The pipelines were assumed to be manufactured from chromium steel sheets. The tanks for interim storage were assumed to be made from carbon steel, and processing was not included. The weight of a tank was estimated to be *ca.* two-thirds of its capacity based on manufacturer data [35]. For all infrastructure, a lifetime of 25 years was used consistently with TEA analysis in Section 2.2. It was assumed that the electricity used is a European average mix.

Shipping was modeled as a diesel tanker barge including the operation of refrigeration also running on diesel fuel. Two classes of tanker barges were modeled: a low capacity (350 t on average) for the hub and spoke shipping strategy, and a high capacity (1150 t on average) for the milk round strategy. The size and fuel consumption of the two classes of tanker barges were based on data from [36]. The Ecoinvent v. 3.8 database [37] was used for the background system, i.e. all the processes upstream and downstream of the foreground system.

Life cycle environmental impacts were calculated in terms of the global warming potential and also the impacts on ecosystem and human health, based on the LCI data using the ReCiPe 2016 LCIA methodology [38], [39].

Table 3. Life cycle inventories per 1 t_{CO2} for the CO₂ transport cases from Table 1.

Case number	Case name	Specific power			Materials	
		Compression	Liquefaction	Shipping	Pipeline	Storage
		(kWh/t _{CO2})	(kWh/t _{CO2})	(t _{steel} km/t _{CO2})	(kg _{steel} /t _{CO2})	(kg _{steel} /t _{CO2})
1	Pipeline, 35 bar, Yara	34	25	0	0.072	0
2	Pipeline, 35 bar, AMG	34	25	0	0.14	0
3	Pipeline, 110 bar, Yara	35	29	0	0.091	0
4	Pipeline, 110 bar, AMG	35	29	0	0.18	0
5	Ship, hub and spoke, Yara	33	25	11	0	0.006
6	Ship, hub and spoke, AMG	33	25	13	0	0.007
7	Ship, milk round, Yara, North	33	25	34	0	0.042
8	Ship, milk round, Yara, South	33	25	30	0	0.038
9	Ship, milk round, AMG, North	33	25	36	0	0.040
10	Ship, milk round, AMG, South	33	25	22	0	0.034

2.4. Tiered Multi-Objective Optimization (TMOO) model

To determine the optimal strategy for intra-cluster CO₂ transport in the NSP region among the number of feasible design cases (see Table 1), a multi-objective optimization method was applied utilizing the Pareto efficiency criterion that achieves a best compromise between the different objectives [40]. The Pareto optimal solutions were constructed using the weighted sum method [40], where the cost and the integral environmental impacts of the CO₂ transport case k from Table 1 were combined in a single objective function:

$$J(\mathbf{w}, k) = \sum_{i=1}^4 w_i J_{i,k} \quad (7)$$

In this equation, $J_{i,k}$ are the normalized objective functions associated with the cost ($i=1$), and three environmental impact categories [the impacts on global warming ($i=2$), human health ($i=3$), and ecosystems ($i=4$)], evaluated for the infrastructure design case k , and $\mathbf{w} = (w_1, w_2, w_3, w_4)$ is the vector of weighting factors applied to the four objectives $J_{i,k}$ satisfying the constraint $\sum_{i=1}^4 w_i = 1$.

The normalized objectives $J_{i,k}$ in equation (7) were calculated as:

$$J_{i,k} = \frac{O_{i,k} - \min_j O_{i,j}}{\max_j O_{i,j} - \min_j O_{i,j}} \quad (8)$$

where $O_{j,k}$ are the combined costs ($i=1$) calculated as described in Section 2.2, and the environmental impacts ($i=2,3,4$), obtained from the LCA in Section 2.3, evaluated for the design case k .

For the synthetic objective function $J(\mathbf{w}, k)$, the minimization problem was formulated as:

$$\min_k J(\mathbf{w}, k) \quad (9)$$

This problem was solved for various combinations of weighting factors w_i , sampled in the range between 0 and 1, with the increment of 0.1. This resulted in a set of optimal solutions for the CO₂ transport infrastructure corresponding to a Pareto front, where the balance is achieved between the costs and the environmental impacts.

The Pareto optimal solutions were obtained first for the full set of CO₂ transport cases (these are referred to as 'tier 1' optimal solutions); then the optimization was repeated on the reduced set of cases, excluding the previously identified optimal solutions, to obtain other optimal solution tiers (sub-optimal to tier 1) until the number of cases was exhausted.

3. Results

3.1. Costs and environmental impacts of intra-cluster CO₂ transport

This section describes the results of TEA and LCA of CO₂ transport solutions in the cluster, along with the results of multi-objective optimization using the TMOO of the CO₂ transport cases for the base-line scenario assuming the immediate implementation of the infrastructure project and using the current electricity mix.

Figure 3 (a) shows the results of calculation of the total cost (CAPEX + OPEX) of CO₂ transport in the NSP cluster per functional unit (1 t_{CO2} transported) for eight cases from Table 1. The two shipping milk round strategies involving uneconomical transport of CO₂ over long distance on the last leg of the milk round (cases 8 and 9 in Table 1) were discarded. As can be seen in Figure 3 (a), the CO₂ pipeline transport strategies have a lower financial cost than shipping. The 35 bar pipeline strategy has a slightly lower cost than the 110 bar one, with its higher pipeline cost being outweighed by the savings in conditioning (compression and liquefaction) costs. Overall, the pipeline costs are dominated by OPEX related to energy consumption in CO₂ compression and liquefaction. These conditioning costs are also very similar for the shipping strategies. Of the shipping strategies, the milk round is the most economical. This is because servicing the entire network using a single ship benefits from economies of scale [29]. Although the average distance that a tonne of CO₂ travels is greater in this strategy, the mileage cost (€/t_{CO2}.km) makes a minor contribution to the financial cost (0.14-0.23 €/t_{CO2} vs. 8.4 €/t_{CO2} for the tonnage cost). The intermediate storage requirement for the milk round shipping is *ca.* 7.16 kt_{CO2} which is considerably larger than *ca.* 1.14 kt_{CO2} for the hub and spoke strategy. This is due to the longer shipping cycle for the milk round. However, the cost of storage is very low compared to the other cost components in the shipping strategies, so the impact on overall cost is negligible.

Figure 3. Total cost (CAPEX + OPEX) (a) and the life cycle environmental impacts (b, c, d) of CO₂ transport in the NSP cluster per functional unit (1 t_{CO2} transported) for eight cases from Table 1. The cost breakdown is shown for different process stages.

Figure 3 (b-d) shows the results of calculation of the life cycle environmental impacts of the NSP intra-cluster CO₂ transport on global warming, human health, and ecosystems, per functional unit (1 t_{CO2} transported) for the same eight cases as in Figure 3 (a). The results in Figure 3 (b-d) show relatively small differences between the environmental impacts for each of the four CO₂ transportation modes. Across all the cases and impact categories, environmental impacts differ at most by 12%, except for human health results which vary by up to 20%. The environmental impacts are driven by the electricity consumption for the CO₂ conditioning, similar to the cost results. The contribution of compression and liquefaction ranges between 52-54% and 40-42% for the three impact categories considered, on average across the eight selected cases. Unlike financial costs, the impact of shipping is relatively low, contributing at most to 8% of the impact on ecosystems for the shipping milk round strategy (Yara south). Finally, the pipeline infrastructure has a notable impact on human health, especially for the AMG off-take point due to a thicker pipe, where the consumption of additional steel in the pipeline contributes to 11% and 12% of the impact on human health at 35 bar and 110 bar, respectively.

Figure 4 shows the plots of environmental impacts against CO₂ transport costs for the ten cases from Table 1, with the tiered Pareto fronts predicted using the TMOO model of Section 2.4. These results illustrate the balance between costs and environmental impacts. In the plots, all the results (costs and the environmental impacts) are expressed per functional unit (1 t_{CO2} transported). As shown in Figure 4, the first tier Pareto front, which represents the ultimate optimal set of CO₂ transport solutions, includes the low-pressure pipeline with the off-take at Yara (case 1 in Table 1) and the shipping hub and spoke case with the off-take from Yara (case 5 in Table 1). The former (case 1) shows the lowest score across all criteria considered, except for human health where the latter (case 5) shows a lower impact by 2%. However, this 2% reduction in human health impact comes at the price of a 54% increase in network costs. Therefore, the low-pressure pipeline with Yara off-take can be considered as the optimal CO₂ intra-

cluster transport strategy for the NSP. The milk round strategy achieves a considerable cost saving (20 %) compared to the hub and spoke strategy, at the expense of minor increases ($\sim 1\%$) to global warming and ecosystems impacts.

Figure 4. Plots of environmental impacts versus costs for CO₂ transport solutions from Table 1, including tiers of Pareto optimal solutions obtained using TMOO method. Tier 1 solutions are both optimal, depending on the weight given to environmental impacts against costs. If Tier 1 solutions are excluded, then Tier 2 becomes optimal, which can be interpreted as a “Plan B”. Tier 3 follows the same logic. The final three solutions were not included in the TMOO.

4. Summary and conclusions

In the present study, a new and flexible approach to multi-objective optimization of CO₂ transport where cost and environmental impacts are balanced using tiered multi-objective optimization method was developed and applied to optimize CO₂ transport and conditioning within the NSP industrial cluster involving five emitters. Two main modes of transportation were compared, including a pipeline network and shipping with barges, and ten potential implementations were analyzed for the four main CO₂ transport strategies, including low and high pressure pipelines, and also milk round and hub and spoke shipping strategies. The results in Section 3 showed that for the intra-cluster CO₂ aggregation, low pressure pipeline operated at 35 bar is the optimal solution, with the lowest costs and environmental impacts (€12.5/tCO₂ and 22.9 kgCO₂-eq./tCO₂, respectively), followed by ship hub and spoke as a second preferable solution that have higher cost (by ca 37%) and global warming impact (by ca 2%). Across all CO₂ transport strategies and cases studied, the electricity consumption for CO₂ conditioning was the main source of costs (ca 44%) and environmental impacts (ca 96%).

A hierarchy of sub-optimal solutions was also obtained to provide the decision makers with the option of choosing alternative strategies, should implementation of the optimal strategy be impractical.

Further work will include investigation of the impacts of construction delays and electricity mix on the optimal solution for CO₂ transport.

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